

Hygrothermal Ageing of Fibrous Composites

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ABSTRACT

The effects of hygrothermal ageing upon the micromechanisms of fracture of glass fibres and carbon fibres in epoxy are described. A collection of failure data based on the direct observation of fibres debonding, breaking and pulling out of a cracked matrix is displayed in empirical failure diagrams. These diagrams show how moisture and time in a hygrothermal ageing experiment affect these micro-mechanisms of crack extension. Fracture maps based on models of fracture are used to interpret certain hygrothermal ageing phenomena.

INTRODUCTION

Fibrous composites fail by a number of simultaneous mechanisms: fibre fracture, matrix cracking, fibre-matrix decohesion (fibre debonding), fibre pull-out, and so forth. Each one has certain characteristics. The variability of fibre strength and fibre-matrix bond strength, for example, affects two characteristic failure parameters, fibre debond length and fibre pull-out length. These parameters are sensitive to the size and distribution of flaws along the fibre length, and to the environment, moisture and temperature. Such failure processes and how they are affected by hygrothermal ageing in air are important because they determine the time-dependent failure of the composite.

Toughness Relationships

Each mechanism of fracture can be modelled, and the associated dissipation of energy described, by a set of equations of the generalised form

$$\gamma = f(\sigma_f, E_f, V_f, d_f, \epsilon_o, l_d, l_p, \text{etc}) .$$

These are the variables which describe the properties of the composite and its microstructural features: fibre strength σ_f and stiffness E_f , fibre diameter d_f and volume fraction V_f ; fibre-matrix misfit strain, ϵ_o , which produces a frictional force between fibre and matrix; also fibre debond length l_d and fibre pull-out length l_p , and so on. Some of these parameters are constants for a given composite, d_f and V_f , are examples; others may change with time in an hygrothermal ageing experiment, σ_f and ϵ_o are examples.

Although we have satisfactory physical models of fracture that lead us to a set of toughness equations [1, 2], their development to take into account environmental effects is incomplete, and there exists little data on which to evaluate them.

Failure Diagrams

One approach is to assemble fractographic data based on the two failure parameters l_d and l_p , which we can measure. The data are then displayed in empirical failure diagrams to show how the humidity or time in hygrothermal ageing experiments influences the particular failure mode. A failure diagram has 2 axes: cumulative probability and fibre debond length or fibre pull-out length. The diagram is constructed by assembling a large collection of data of l_d and l_p . We then calculate the probability P of observing a fibre debonding or pulling out over a distance greater or smaller than a particular length l . We first measure, using an optical microscopic technique [3, 4], the distances over which the bundles of fibre debond and pull-out in monotonic loading. We arrange serially $j = 1, 2, 3 \dots N$ values of debond length and pull-out length in increasing order of length. The probability P is defined as

$$P = (j - 0.5)/N$$

A Weibull statistical analysis is then used to best fit the assembled data to a curve which is described by the equation

$$P = 1 - \exp(-l/l_0)^m .$$

l_0 and m are material constants. A characteristic length \bar{l} of a set of data points can be expressed as

$$\bar{l} = \int_{l_1}^{l_n} m(l/l_0)^{m-1} \exp[-(l/l_0)^m] dl .$$

Fracture Maps

Alternatively, the fracture behaviour can be summarised as a theoretical fracture map: a diagram with, for example, fibre strength as one axis and fibre-matrix misfit strain as the other. Superimposed onto the map may be contour lines of the predicted values of l_d and l_p , together with theoretical toughness values. These maps are constructed by analysing the fibre debonding and fibre-pull out mechanisms and combining the predictions of l_d and l_p with models of toughening [1, 2]. The superposition of experimental toughness, pull-out and debond length data onto the map enables the effect of time or humidity upon certain intrinsic material parameters to be read directly from the map.

FAILURE DIAGRAMS

Failure Analysis of grp

Figure 1 shows typical failure diagrams for a model unidirectional glass fibre-epoxy composite [3, 4]. The data are collected from about 10 specimens that have been exposed to different humidities at 100°C for times that range between 1 h and 4 weeks, and then fractured in monotonic loading. We observe the displacement of fibre debond length data to higher values during the initial 72 h of hygrothermal ageing at 95% rh, followed by a steady shift to lower values after 3 days. For some reason, the data collected on unexposed material ($t = 0$) appears to be out of position*.

*We believe that residual compressive stresses are set up into the matrix when a sample is cooled from its fabrication (or ageing) temperature of 100°C to room

GLASS FIBRE - EPOXY RESIN.

Fig. 1: Distribution of glass fibre debond length and pull-out length after exposure to 100°C, 95% rh. Also the work of fracture as a function of ageing time. The numbers on the curves refer to ageing time in hours.

GLASS FIBRE - EPOXY RESIN.

Fig. 2: Distribution of glass fibre debond length and pull-out length after exposure to 100°C, 0% rh. Also the work of fracture as a function of ageing time. The numbers on the curves refer to ageing time in hours.

Measurements of fibre pull-out lengths are about an order of magnitude smaller than the observed fibre debond lengths. The data points fall into two distinct bands; larger values for up to 3 days exposure time, smaller values for longer ageing times.

temperature. In the case of the unaged samples, about 30 days lapsed before testing, sufficient time to allow these residual stresses to relax. The mismatch strain ϵ_0 between fibre and matrix therefore falls which causes the fibre debond length to appear greater than we would have expected if the sample was tested immediately after fabrication (see section on Use of Fracture Maps)

In Fig. 2 are shown data for ageing in dry air (0% rh). Each set of data of debond lengths do not superimpose but are displaced relative to one another. For short times, the debonded fibres lengthen and then fall; and after 2 weeks, they increase in length once again.

These subtle movements of failure data match the changes in toughness with ageing.

Failure Analysis of cfrp

Similar diagrams show the distribution of failure data for pulled out carbon fibres in epoxy (Fig. 3). For this particular system, fibre debonding is very small. We observe an incubation period of about 3 days at 95% rh before fibre pull-out lengths begin to shorten slightly. This relates to a gradual fall in toughness with time.

The sets of data collected after ageing in dry air are similar to those obtained for moist atmospheres (Fig. 4).

CARBON FIBRE-EPOXY
RESIN.

Fig. 3: Distribution of carbon fibre pull-out length after exposure to 100°C, 95% rh. Also the work of fracture as a function of ageing time. The numbers on the curves refer to ageing time in hours.

CARBON FIBRE-EPOXY
RESIN.

Fig. 4: Distribution of carbon fibre pull-out length after exposure to 100°C, 0% rh. Also the work of fracture as a function of ageing time. The numbers on the curves refer to ageing time in hours.

WORK OF FRACTURE

The toughness of a given composite can be estimated by making measurements of work of fracture. We do this by integrating the load-deflection curve obtained in 3-point bending and dividing by twice the cross-sectional area of the fibres. Experimental work of fracture data for glass fibres and carbon fibres in epoxy are shown in Figs. 1 - 4. For dry air, a precipitous fall in work of fracture of grp occurs during the first hour of exposure. Recovery is almost immediate and the work of fracture appears to increase but at a slow rate. Exposure to high humidity causes the work of fracture to fall by about 10% in the first 1 h. Recovery is complete within the next 2 days or so. This, however, is followed by a fall in work of fracture over the next 3 weeks and longer.

In the case of the carbon fibre composite, a small increase in work of fracture during the first 1 h of exposure to 95% rh is followed by a gradual decrease in toughness after 100 h or so but the overall decrease in toughness is slight. In dry conditions the work of fracture decreases slowly over 100 h and again the changes are small.

To clarify the effects of ageing at room temperature, some samples were tested immediately after manufacture; others were stored for 30 days in a desiccator and then fractured. We observed that the work of fracture of the grp immediately after manufacture was about 20% lower than similar samples aged for 30 days. In contrast, samples containing carbon fibres were about 15% less tough after ageing.

Our explanation for these changes in work of fracture of both composite systems is based on residual compressive stresses in the epoxy set up during cooling from the fabrication and ageing temperature of 100°C to room temperature. We believe that samples tested immediately after manufacture contain these "frozen-in" stresses. Any residual stress may relax with time and the compressive force or mismatch strain between fibre and matrix decreases. It follows naturally that the stress on the glass fibre at debonding and the "frictional" interfacial shear stress during pull-out of the carbon fibres will be lower in samples that have been stored for a considerable time before testing. The magnitudes of these stresses are important since they determine the energy dissipated when a glass fibre debonds and a carbon fibre pulls out of its socket [1, 2]. The fracture energy of glass fibres in epoxy falls as the fibre debond length decreases, which is consistent with our observations. For carbon fibres in epoxy, the work of fibre pull-out is dependent upon the frictional interfacial shear stress (for a constant pull-out length) which again is consistent with our observations.

However, these arguments fail to explain the low measurement of work of fracture of glass fibres in epoxy after 1 h exposure in hot, dry air, and the recovery during the next 24 h. We therefore cannot be absolutely confident in the data for 1 h although this data was reproducible with repeated testing.

The origin of the increase in work of fracture of the glass fibre composite over 700 h in hot, dry air may be connected with a degradation of the fibre-matrix bond, perhaps as a result of polymerisation of a silane coating on the surface of the glass [5]. The fibre debond stress falls and the debond length increases.

USE OF FRACTURE MAPS

Hygrothermal Ageing of grp

A fracture map for a [0/90]E-glass fibre-epoxy laminate is shown in Fig. 5. The axes are fibre-matrix misfit strain ϵ_0 and fibre strength. Superimposed on the map are experimental data points of critical strain energy release rate γ (toughness) measured in 3-point bending [2]. The arrows show the direction in which movement of data occurs with increasing ageing time in 95% rh, 100°C, up to about 100 h. We believe that absorbed moisture in the resin causes the matrix to swell, the mismatch strain to fall, and the fibre strength to degrade. This is read directly from the map. Changes in toughness from about 30 kJ/m² to 12 kJ/m² are principally due to the degradation of fibre strength by a stress-corrosion

Fig. 5: Variation of glass fibre debond length, pull-out length, and work of fracture with changes in fibre strength and fibre-matrix misfit strain. The experimental data of work of fracture and the arrows show the effect of increasing time.

process, together with a fall in residual compressive stress in the matrix or ϵ_0 . The map shows these changes together with changes in debond length and pull-out length.

Hygrothermal Ageing of cfrp

Two maps for the model unidirectional fibre composites are shown in Figs. 6 and 7 [1]. The axes are G_2 , an interface parameter which affects the fibre debond stress, the frictional interfacial shear stress τ_f , and fibre strength σ_f . The measured changes in fibre pull-out length and work of fracture cannot be due to the same mechanism as proposed for the glass fibre composite. The small decrease of fibre pull-out length for cfrp exposed to 95% rh and slight fall in work of fracture is related to a decrease in value of fibre debond stress and an increase in frictional interfacial shear stress during fibre pull-out. We believe this is due to a thermal effect since our observations of fibre pull-out length and work of fracture were similar in wet and dry environments.

CONCLUSIONS

Complicated phenomena associated with the fracture of fibrous composites during hygrothermal ageing can be described using empirical failure diagrams. Alternatively, theoretical fracture maps can be constructed and changes of certain material parameters and toughness with ageing can be read directly from the map. Comparison of one failure diagram and another and between fracture maps can show the differences in failure behaviour of various classes of fibre composites.

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Fig. 6: Contours of predicted carbon fibre pull-out length (mm). The variation of τ_f with time during exposure to 95% rh is shown by the data points.

Fig. 7: Contours of predicted work of fracture (kJ/m^2) for carbon fibres in epoxy. The variation of G_2 and τ_f with time during exposure to 95% rh is shown by the data points

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